

**ANALYSIS OF INFORMATION OF EMBASSY RELATIONS IN
ABDURAZZAK SAMARKANDI'S WORK "MATLAI SADAYN WA
MAJMAI BAHRAIN"**

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Annotation We can get a lot of interesting information, that is considered as a valuable source for covering the process of socio-political, cultural, educational and embassy relations of the Timurid period by Abdurazzak Samarkandi's work "Matlai Sadayn wa Majmai Bahrain". In the work we can get acquainted with more than 200 information about the rulers, governors, governors and other officials of the Timurids of neighboring countries, as well as mutual internal diplomatic relations. From this work we can learn about some diplomatic relations, albeit brief, not only of the Timurids, but also of other dynasties that ruled at that time. This article analyzes the information about the embassy relations of the Timurids on local relations.

Key words: Amir Timur, Timurids, Abdurazzak Samarkandi, "Matlai sadayn wa majmai bahrain", diplomacy, embassy, struggle for the throne

Introduction.

Abdurazzak Samarkandi's Matlai Sadayn wa Majmai Bahrain is a valuable source on the Timurid period. The most valuable parts of the work, which have been fully translated into Uzbek, were involved in the study. [1, 2] This translation has created a conducive environment for use in many studies.

In the Uzbek translation chronicles, the main historical events that took place in the territory of the Timurid state from the death of Amir Timur to the beginning of Hussein Boykaro's accession to the throne (1405-1470), especially in Khorasan and Movarounnahr. These parts of the work are valuable in that they contain events that the author himself witnessed more and is contemporary. The forerunners of

Matlai Sadayn wa Majmai Bahrain were written by Hafiz Abru by partially supplementing Zubdat ut Tavorix. Abdurazzak Samarkandi attached great importance to the description of the cultural life of that period and the creative activity of the Timurid rulers and princesses. He also attached great importance to the description of the Timurid state's diplomatic relations with China, India and other countries. The study of the cultural processes of that period from sources written by an author who was a direct witness to the events ensures the reliability of the data. [3]

The diplomacy of the Timurid period is characterized not only by intense relations with foreign countries, but also by interactions with the governors of the vassal states, representatives of the opposition, representatives of the people. The history of diplomatic relations during this period has been studied by scholars from many countries around the world. In particular, we can study more than 100 studies by Western and Eastern scientists. This research is mainly limited to the diplomatic relations of the Timurid state with China [4], India [5], Egypt and European countries. During the study of the parts of the work involved in the study, more than 200 pieces of information related to diplomacy were encountered. We can conditionally divide them into different groups.

These include embassy relations between the princes during the struggle for the throne, first after Amir Timur and then after the death of Shakhruh Mirza; After Shakhruh Mirza and other Timurid princes consolidated their thrones, embassy relations with neighboring countries - China, India, Egypt, Room, Azerbaijan (Turkmen) and relations with frequently changing rulers, as well as diplomatic relations between at least other countries.

The main part.

After Amir Timur drove out the foreign invaders from Movarounnahr and established a single state, his next main goal was to ensure the security of the country. Sahibkiran had to prevent the invasion of Movarounnahr by the Mongols, the Golden Horde, and the Elkhanid state, and to ensure the peace of the people. To

achieve this goal, he initially used peaceful, diplomatic means. We turn our attention to the following entries in "Timur's Statutes": "I did nine parts of the affairs of state by council, event and consultation, and one part by the power of the sword." [6] Another important aspect of Amir Timur's activity was that he paid great attention to international cooperation. Sahibkiran was well aware that without such cooperation there would be no independence. The participation of the young princes in the embassy ceremonies had a positive effect on their future work. At the age of 10, Ulugbek attended the reception of ambassadors from China and Spain. [7]

Amir Timur established diplomatic relations not only with neighboring countries, but also with distant countries such as France, Spain, England, Byzantium, sent ambassadors to them and received their ambassadors in his kingdom. After the death of Amir Timur (1405) the struggle for the throne culminated. His death was initially kept secret, but the news reached Khalil Sultan, who was in Tashkent and Sayram, first, as well as other princes everywhere. [8] Meanwhile, Khalil Sultan ascended the throne of Samarkand and proclaimed himself ruler of the country. [1] Shah Rukh Mirza, who ruled in Herat and considered himself the ruler of the kingdom, did not like this situation and withdrew his army to Movaraunnahr.

The first information about the embassy in the play is given in the description of this event. When Shah Rukh Mirza set out and reached the anchor of Prince Boyazid, he sent a man named Hamza Qatuqu as an envoy to Khalil Sultan and sent him a letter. The text of the letter is given in full in the play. We can say from the content of the embassy and the letter that it was to govern the state on the basis of mutual agreement without fighting. In response to this embassy, Khalil Sultan's envoys also come and the text of their letters is also quoted in the play. The content of the letter states that Khalil Sultan fully agreed with the terms of Shakhruh Mirza. But, the developing process of events does not correspond to the content of the letter, that is, Khalil Sultan starts a fight.

When the embassy fails, Sheikh Nuriddin, who is more experienced, is appointed to the embassy. Sheikh Nuriddin's speech in the presence of Khalil Sultan

was quoted in the play and was mainly aimed at reconciling the two sides in the style of admonition. This embassy yielded results and Shah Rukh Mirza's army headed for Herat.

After the death of Amir Timur, Mirza Pir Muhammad, the son of Umarshaikh Mirza, who ruled in Sheroz, decided to recognize the rule of Shakhruh Mirza in consultation with the emirs on the future fate of the state. The embassy sent in this connection gives good result.

Amir Idiku sent envoys to Herat from Barman Kerman to announce the recognition of the rule of Shakhruh Mirza.

Recognizing the authority of Shah Rukh, Mirza Pir Muhammad, who received various instructions from him, began to strengthen the work of full regulation of the affairs of the provinces under his control. Amir Idiku sent envoys to Barlos to persuade him to submit, but the ambassadors sent did not work. From this it is clear that Amir Idiku sent ambassadors to Shah Rukh, fully acknowledging his authority and wishing to govern himself fully through him.

Embassy of Hamadan from Mirza Iskandar to Shiraz to Mirza Pir Muhammad ibn Umarshaikh. The purpose of this embassy was to warn Pir Muhammad Mirza of the danger posed by Mirza Umar and to unite against him. However, Mirza Pir Muhammad, who feared that Mirza Iskandar would come to his country, did not want him to come and enmity arose between them. Eventually they agree and start working together.

From Isfahan, an envoy named Haji Musafir was sent by Mirza Rustam to Mirza Umar in Hamadan. While Mirza 'Umar was drawing troops to invade Iraq and Persia, Mirza Rustam, who was ruling in Isfahan at the time, sent envoys to make peace and a peace treaty was reached.

Another peculiarity of diplomatic relations is that any ruler sent ambassadors to indicate that he was coming towards lands belonging to another ruler, stating the purpose of his visit. Such embassies were necessary regardless of the presence of parents, sons, brothers, and other relatives. Otherwise, the intention was not good

and led to a fight. One such embassy was appointed by Shakhruh Mirza to Mirza Mironshah. Mironshah Mirza goes to Shakhruh Mirza and does not send ambassadors warning him of the purpose of his arrival. Hearing that Mirza Mironshah was coming to Khorasan, Shakhruh Mirza sent Amirs Hasan Sufi Tarkhan, Jahanmulk and Feruzshah as ambassadors to find out the purpose of this visit and to prevent a possible battle. Accompanied by five thousand cavalries, the ambassadors return with full agreement. In fact, it can be concluded that Mirza Mironshah's goal was not to fight. But it is also possible that Mironshah may have hoped for the throne, including that an agreement had been reached. Given the power of the princes at the time, this seems impossible.

A number of embassies between Amir Suleiman Shah and Shakhruh Mirza are also mentioned in the play. After the execution of Sultan Hussein, an ally of Amir Suleiman the Magnificent, he embarked on a path of discord. In this connection, he sent envoys to Shakhruh Mirza and demanded the expulsion of Amir Shahmalik and the execution of Nushirvan Barlos. As a result, the battle begins. Before the battle began, he sent ambassadors a second time, asking to send his son-in-law, Amir Abdusamad. Amir Abdusamad, who was sent at the request of Amir Suleiman Shah, repeatedly tried to dissuade Amir Suleiman Shah from the path of the opposition, but he refused, causing an inevitable battle and ending in his defeat.

Ambassadors came to Shakhruh Mirza from Amir Cherkas ibn Amir Tumon. This embassy was sent by Amir Timur to find out that the black Tatar Turkmens who had been brought to Movarounnahr from the Roman province had fled to the Khorasan side and what to do with them. According to the order, all black Tatar Turkmens were captured and brought to Shakhruh Mirzo.

Mirza Pir Muhammad ibn Jahangir sent envoys from Balkh province to Khalil Sultan in Samarkand, claiming that Sahibkiran was the Crown Prince, in response to which Khalil Sultan replied that Allah had given him the throne and disobeyed his terms and caused the war to break out. The battle ends with the defeat of Mirza Pir Muhammad.

Details of more than thirty embassies between princes and emirs during this period are recorded. Most of them were aimed at a truce of friendship, the prevention of inevitable wars and the peaceful settlement of the issue. In analyzing the data, embassies were sometimes found to be effective, sometimes ineffective. The reason for this was not due to the ignorance or rhetoric of the ambassadors. In many cases, rulers overestimate or underestimate their power, believe in help that may come from the other side, and so on. The ambassadors were mostly experienced emirs, sheikhs, and dignitaries. In some cases, ordinary navkars also served as ambassadors. They carried letters from the embassy stating the main purpose.

The struggle for the throne, which began after the death of Amir Timur, began in the same way when Shakhruh Mirza died. The princes intensify their efforts in order to take advantage of the situation. The struggle for the throne continued until he took full control of the throne, culminating again with his death.

After Shakhruh's death, Ulugbek Mirzo, who considered all his lands as his own, received the news that Muhammad Jogi's youngest son, Abobakr Balkh, had taken the lands of Shiberghan, Kunduz and Badakhshan as his own. Then he sends envoys and tries to turn him to his side. When Shah Rukh heard that Abdullatif, who was carrying Mirza's body, had been captured in Nishapur, it was decided that one way to save him was to make peace with Mirza Alouddawla. Nizamuddin Mirak Mahmud Sadr goes as ambassador and a truce is reached. It is reported that Mirzo Ulugbek sent more ambassadors to prevent a possible battle in Balkh due to the feud between Mirzo Abdullatif and Alouddavla.

When Mirzo Ulugbek set out in 1449 to conquer Mashhad and other parts of Khorasan and reached Rodikon, Abul Qasim Babur's envoys arrived and declared that he would fully recognize his rule. When Abul Qasim Babur was occupying Herat, Mirzo Ulugbek sent envoys to his father to betray him, saying that he had set out to conquer Khorasan and would not let them pass through Jaihun and was loyal to him. But Abul Qasim Babur cannot keep Herat in his hands for long. Mirza Sultan Muhammad, who had set out to fortify Persia and Iraq and conquer Khorasan, sent

an envoy to formalize after Muhammad Bistom and warned his brother Mirza Abul Qasim Babur. The throne of Samarkand passed to Abdullatif, and the throne of Herat to Sultan Muhammad. It was noted that good relations have been established between them and embassies have been exchanged several times.

Sultan Muhammad was always thinking of conquering Khurasan. During the reign of Mirza Abul Qasim Babur (1450), Mirza sent a man named Bahauddin Khoja Mawlana to Isfahan to Muhammad Sultan Muhammad. Sultan Muhammad, who had first made peace, then went to war again and was defeated and executed.

Mirza Abul Qasim reported to Babur that envoys from Herat had arrived in Isfahan (1452) and that the events there, that is, Mirza Alouddawla had captured Herat.

Since Mirza Abul Qasim Babur captured Herat and then set out to capture Movarounnahr (1454), the ambassadors Abu Sa'id came from Samarkand as Hodja Nizamuddin Mawdud and Jamaluddin Fathullah Tabrizi as ambassadors with the intention of turning them away from this path. But the emirs laugh at them and don't take it well. It is noted that a number of other embassies were exchanged between the two Timurids. The ambassadors bring many books along with gift greetings. In particular, Mirzo Ulugbek's "Ziji Sultani", Abul Vafo Khorezmi's "Lubbul-albob".

It is reported that his eldest son, Jalaluddin Shah Mahmud, who ascended the throne for some time after the death of Abul Qasim Babur, received a number of embassies. A number of embassies were also established between Mirza Sultan Ibrahim ibn Alouddaw, who had taken Herat from Jalal al-Din Shah Mahmud, and Abu Sa'id, who ruled the Samarkand throne.

When Mirza Sultan Ibrahim ascended the throne of Herat (1458), he sent envoys to Abu Sa'id and offered friendship and goodwill. Abu Sa'id says that he sees him as his own child and will give him any territory other than Herat. It means the need to unite against the Turkmen. Mirza Alouddavla and Abul Qasim Babur, who were on the Iberian and Siberian sides at that time, set out for Herat on the occasion of Babur's death and sent an envoy to his son to announce his arrival. When Mirza

Jahanshah Turkmen occupied Herat for some time (1458), many ambassadors from the surrounding lands came and brought gifts and greetings. The play also provides information about a number of embassies between Abu Sa'id and Mirza Jahanshah. It is noted that the author of the work also served as an ambassador between Sultan Hussein and Abu Sa'id, who ruled in Astrobod. When Abdurazzaq visited Samarkand's Jurjan province, he witnessed the events surrounding Sultan Hussein and informed Abu Sa'id about his obedience.

One of the peculiarities of *Matlai Sadayn* is that the coverage of embassy relations was carried out not only by Shakhruh Mirza and his descendants, but also by other Timurid princes, other dynasties and emirs.

Mirza Abul Qasim Babur fought many battles to subdue Sari province. Aware of his defeat, Amir Sayyid Muhammad Abul Qasim offered to make peace and asked him to send envoys.

According to the embassy, Shamsuddin Muhammad Bukhari will return to Sari province to make peace. Most of the information about the embassies mentioned in the play includes the names of the ambassadors. However, the fact that the ambassador's name is not mentioned is also significant.

Conclusion.

Analyzing the diplomatic data of the work, we can get essential information on the socio-political, cultural and educational processes in Movarounnahr, Khorasan, Persia, Iraq, Azerbaijan, China, Dashti Kipchak, Mongolia, India and other countries in the period from the death of Amir Timur to the first years of Hussein Boykaro's accession to the throne (1405-1470). In particular, along with the analysis of local embassy relations, we can explore the subtleties of the struggle for the throne that took place at that time. More than 200 of information in this area serve as a necessary source for research.

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